

FORMATION OF INTEREST IN READING BOOKS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Karimova Jahona

1st stage master of Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

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Abstract. *This article was formed on the basis of promotion of book reading, which is the basis for the emergence of the Third Renaissance of Uzbekistan, the measures for its establishment, the history of its creation and foundation.*

Keywords: *book, reader, publisher, newspaper, magazine, written message, bibliophiles.*

Emphasizing that there will not be a special state document - a curriculum, which is divided by academic years and defines the content and scope of knowledge, skills and qualifications that must be mastered by students in primary grades. A book is necessary. We had to develop such a program, but it could be the result of a successful solution to the general task - to identify the scientific and methodological basis of the training course and to formulate a reasonable one. In other words, we need to express reading as a way of changing the knowledge and reality acquired by a growing and developing person, and describe the significant components of the set of learning that provide the uniqueness of the planned educational activity. It was necessary, the starting point of reflection and analysis should be the book.

The study of works dedicated to the book and the reader allows to emphasize that the book represents the most complex phenomenon among the objects included in the educational activities of elementary school students.

Due to its complexity, the "book" still does not have a single interpretation. As the French writer, literary critic, sociologist Robert Escarpit noted: "Like all living beings, the book does not fit within the strict boundaries of definitions. No one has yet been able to give a clear and stable definition to it." Bibliographers distinguish the following definitions, which are most commonly used in connection with the concept of "book":

A book is a means of communication between people, a mass media tool.

A book is a synonym of a literary work, a product of the author's work.

Book - publication - publishing - product of polygraphy activity.

A book is a special form of publication, different from a newspaper, magazine, booklet, album, etc. The form of certain constructive organization of book pages...

A book is a form of organization of a written message.

What is the main meaning of the book for the pedagogue who forms the reader and for the students learning the art of independent reading? To solve this question, we turned to the definitions of the book from the point of view of its social importance. One such concise definition is given by A. Gersen: "...the experience expressed in writing and made available for general use is a book." We find such definitions in the definitions of many other great scholars of the past and present who paid attention to the book: "interlocutor", "teacher", "torch", "teacher", "do 'st", "priceless heritage", "world seen through man", "history of peoples", "past experience", "heritage of human mind", "ship of thought", "great miracle discovered by man" - these and similar imaginations acquired from childhood arouse a sense of pride for the person who discovered the

book, as in front of the book as a storage place and a means of conveying the experience that is necessary for us and accumulated by mankind. gives rise to a feeling of dread.

The historical experience of mankind and the mental abilities formed in it are realized not only in the book, but also in "every object created by man - from a hand-held weapon to a modern electronic computing machine." In this sense, the book is not an exception, it is also a "process of thought realization".

But there are two social experiences and individual thoughts in the book: the first time - when creating the manuscript - in language, in words, when the writer has an acute need to make his thoughts the property of a wide circle of people; secondly, it should not be forgotten that it should be done in a purposeful and direct manner and in a subject specially designed to organize a written message addressed to all of us.

But in the "man - book" system, we are not interested in authors and publishers, but in the reader, in which the reader is a beginner - a junior high school student. In independent reading of the given text, the book serves as a word-symbol, and in order to master the ideas directed by the task and the uniqueness of the text image, it is necessary to correctly interpret their system.

The author's thought is hidden from the reader inside the book, as in the fairy tale - "behind seven locks", and the text without someone's help is only for the reader to observe the book as the writers thought. can be perceived through Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, the President of our country, stated that "increasing their interest in reading books is an important guarantee of achieving our great goals."

It is worth noting that Eastern and Western scholars have expressed their unique opinions about reading books in their works.

There is no better bookish friend in the world.

Take care in this sad time.

Stay alone with him, don't hurt him

It's a repeat that brings joy to your soul. Abdurrahman Jami.

The book is the basis of all creativity, creativity and intelligence, a life coach! (Amir Temur)

If we want to be wise, strong and happy, we should start by reading books. (J. Kennedy)

If the book you want to read hasn't been written yet, then you should start writing it. (Morrison)

We are indebted to the book for the main work of our noble benevolences, which strive in the wisest actions. (R. Emerson)

In our study, tasks related to socio-pedagogical and professional activities of librarians in cooperation with elementary school teachers are theoretically based on mutual harmony. One of the important tasks of the school library in the educational process is to form students' interest in reading books. Forming interest in reading books among young students is not only the task of the librarian, but also the task of teachers and parents, and it is a very complex process that requires only a conscious approach. Therefore, we decided to think in detail about the specifics of this process.

Reading culture is a concept in a very broad sense, which includes interest and love for books, wider familiarity with literature, acquiring special knowledge about working with books, as well as acquiring skills that help to fully use books. consists of Reading culture plays an important role in the formation of interest in reading books in primary grades. The culture of

reading allows the student to fully understand the work he is reading, to enjoy it artistically and aesthetically, to understand and evaluate the author's opinion, the idea of the work, in addition, to use books and libraries, to be interested in the reference-bibliographic apparatus. or teaches how to find and use books on relevant subjects. Choosing a book, reading it quickly, recommending the read books to others, and keeping them carefully are also part of their interest in reading books. The concept of "book culture" is used in a broad sense. In particular, this phenomenon requires a certain level of preparation and level from the reader to understand and understand the work. The essence of this phenomenon goes from simply flipping through the book and being able to use it in general, to creative reading, getting to know the author of the book, and reading his work with an in-depth analysis.

In the reading classes, it is important to work on the reading comprehension of the elementary school students. In order to understand not only a scientific book, but also an artistic work, the reader must perform conscious actions to a certain extent and have a certain understanding.

It is important to understand it when reading scientific, social, political literature. This is not an easy task, of course. Not understanding the content of a book is bad, and misunderstanding it is even worse. Various thoughts and questions will arise during the reading process. Agreeing or disagreeing with the author's opinion enriches and deepens the students' opinion.

In the reading culture, having a high taste in choosing literature, having librarianship and bibliographic knowledge, working with books, being able to use new publications, newspapers are also important in forming interest in reading books.

Reading is a common form of mental work. It is the librarian's and the teacher's job to make it even more effective. A reader who organizes study to gain knowledge should know and follow the rules of working with books in order to understand the surrounding environment, nature, humanity, determine his place in life, expand his worldview and improve his professional skills. must do. Another important condition for effective work with the book is to take into account the mental factors of the reader. Before working with the book, the reader should mentally prepare himself: he should be free from thoughts like "I can't read", "I don't understand anything anyway", "reading is difficult". On the contrary, it is necessary to start reading with the confidence that "I can read", "I can manage", "I can understand", "I will achieve my goal". Some students begin to study very quickly, read quickly, hurry, which makes them tired quickly, their eyes get tired, and their nerves get tired.

Another important condition for the proper organization of working with books is to start reading in an organic and consistent manner. This should be maintained throughout the study. It is necessary to read again and again to understand the hard to understand, complex parts of the book. The main thing is not how much to read, but to listen to what is read. Sequence and regularity are important in the learning process. This affects not only the correct distribution of time, but also the full mastery of the selected material.

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